

E5.4
Final Prototype for High Precision Smart
Telemetry
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E5.4 Final Prototype for High Precision Smart Telemetry

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CO	Confidencial solo para miembros del consorcio

Tipo	
PR	Prototipo
RE	Reporte
SP	Especificación
TO	Herramienta
OT	Otro

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List of Acronyms

API	Application Programming Interface
CRUD	Create, Read, Update, Delete
DTO	Data Transfer Object
ETL	Extract, Transform, Load
FPS	Frames Per Second
GKE	Google Kubernetes Engine
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MongoDB	NoSQL Database
RESTful	Representational State Transfer
SLO	Service Level Objective
SLS	Service Level Specification
TM Forum	TeleManagement Forum
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier

Table 1 Acronyms

1. Introduction

Welcome to the Final Prototype for High Precision Smart Telemetry project. This document provides a comprehensive guide for understanding, deploying, and managing the various components involved, including the Alarm Service and Service Quality Management Service. Both services are built using **TM Forum APIs** for high precision and reliable telemetry and service level management. This document also explains the integration with the **E3.6.1**¹. This deliverable is the launch into production of all the components that were finally established in the deliverable **E5.6.1**², which laid the foundations defined in the previous deliverables of this project such as **E2.4**³ or the **E5.2.1**⁴ and represents at the product level, represents a significant advance with respect to **E5.1**⁵, both at the level of components, and communication between them, as well as at the level of implementation and deployment.

2. Overview

The High Precision Smart Telemetry project provides robust and scalable systems for managing telemetry data and service levels. The two main components are:

- **Alarm Service:** Handles high volumes of telemetry data, processes alarms, and stores them in MongoDB. It exposes RESTful endpoints for managing alarms and acknowledged alarms.
- **Service Quality Management Service:** Manages Service Level Objectives (SLOs) and Service Level Specifications (SLs). It processes service levels and stores them in MongoDB. It exposes RESTful endpoints for managing SLOs and SLs.

¹ Guillermo G.C. "6GENABLERS-E3.6.1 Final design for data management and adaptive learning in 6G", I2CAT, June 2024.

² Alberto G.B. "6GENABLERS-E5.6.1 Final design of high precision smart telemetry for 6G optimization", I2CAT, April 2024.

³ Alberto G.B. "6GENABLERS-E2.4 Report on requirements for high-precision smart telemetry", I2CAT, 2023

⁴ Alberto G.B. "6GENABLERS-E5.2.1 Initial design of high precision smart telemetry for 6G optimisation", 2023.

⁵ Alberto G.B. "6GENABLERS-E5.1 Intermediate prototype for high precision smart telemetry", February 2024.

3.Global Architecture

The architecture integrates various components designed for telemetry data collection, processing, and management, supporting the demands of 6G networks. Key components include:

- **OpenTelemetry Collectors:** For collecting telemetry data.
- **Observability Backend:** Consisting of Prometheus, InfluxDB, and Grafana for monitoring and visualizing metrics.
- **ETL Process:** To synchronize the observability backend with the analytics services.
- **Analytics Services:** Utilizing TM Forum APIs for Alarm and Service Quality Management.
- **MongoDB:** For storing telemetry data and configurations.

Figure 1. Global Architecture

4. TM Forum APIs and OpenTelemetry

4.1 TM Forum APIs

TM Forum APIs standardize the management of service quality and alarms. They enable high precision and reliable telemetry by providing structured endpoints for creating, updating, and managing service level specifications and alarms.

4.2 OpenTelemetry

OpenTelemetry is a standardized framework for collecting and exporting telemetry data (metrics, logs, and traces). It ensures data consistency and compatibility across various services and components.

5. Analytics Services

The Analytics Service consists of two main components:

5.1 Alarm Service

The High Precision Smart Telemetry project provides a robust and scalable alarm management system. The Alarm Service handles high volumes of telemetry data, processes alarms, and stores them in MongoDB. The Alarm Service is responsible for managing alarms raised due to violations of service level objectives. It exposes RESTful endpoints for managing alarms and acknowledged alarms.

5.1.1 Architecture

The architecture of the Alarm Service is designed for scalability and maintainability. It includes:

- **Spring Boot Application:** Core logic for alarm management.
- **MongoDB:** Database for storing alarms and acknowledged alarms.
- **Docker:** Containerization for consistent deployment.
- **Kubernetes:** Orchestration for deployment, scaling, and management.

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Figure 2. Alarm Service Architecture

5.1.2 API Models

The API models define the structure of the data used in the Alarm Service. Key models include:

- **Alarm**: Represents an alarm with details such as type, severity, and timestamps.
- **AckAlarmFVO**: Represents an acknowledged alarm with additional metadata.

5.1.3 Repositories

Repositories provide CRUD operations for MongoDB collections:

- **AckAlarmRepository**: Manages MongoAckAlarm entities.
- **AlarmRepository**: Manages MongoAlarm entities.

5.1.4 Services

Services contain the business logic and interact with repositories:

- **Get All Alarms**: Retrieves all alarms.
- **Get Alarm By ID**: Retrieves a specific alarm by its ID.
- **Create Alarm**: Creates a new alarm.
- **Patch Alarm**: Partially updates an existing alarm.
- **Delete Alarm**: Deletes an alarm.
- **Get All Acknowledged Alarms**: Retrieves all acknowledged alarms.

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- **Get Acknowledged Alarm By ID:** Retrieves a specific acknowledged alarm by its ID.
- **Create Acknowledged Alarm:** Creates a new acknowledged alarm.
- **Update Acknowledged Alarm:** Updates an existing acknowledged alarm.
- **Delete Acknowledged Alarm:** Deletes an acknowledged alarm.

Method	Endpoint	Description
GET	/alarms	Retrieves all alarms stored in the MongoDB database.
GET	/alarms/{id}	Retrieves a specific alarm by its ID from the MongoDB database.
POST	/alarms	Creates a new alarm and stores it in the MongoDB database.
PATCH	/alarms/{id}	Partially updates an existing alarm in the MongoDB database.
DELETE	/alarms/{id}	Deletes an alarm from the MongoDB database by its ID.
GET	/ackAlarms	Retrieves all acknowledged alarms stored in the MongoDB database.
GET	/ackAlarms/{id}	Retrieves a specific acknowledged alarm by its ID from the MongoDB database.
POST	/ackAlarms	Creates a new acknowledged alarm and stores it in the MongoDB database.
PUT	/ackAlarms/{id}	Updates an existing acknowledged alarm in the MongoDB database.
DELETE	/ackAlarms/{id}	Deletes an acknowledged alarm from the MongoDB database by its ID.

Table 2. Alarm Services

5.1.5 Utilities

Utilities provide helper methods and configurations:

- **AckAlarmConverter:** Converts between API models and MongoDB models.
- **AckAlarmFVODeserializer:** Custom deserializer for AckAlarmFVO.
- **AlarmConverter:** Converts between API models and MongoDB models.
- **AlarmRefOrValueDeserializer:** Custom deserializer for AlarmRefOrValue.
- **ErrorResponseUtil:** Creates error responses for exceptions.
- **MongoConfig:** Configures MongoDB connection and custom converters.

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- **OffsetDateTimeCodec:** Custom codec for OffsetDateTime.

5.1.6 Configuration

- **MongoConfig:** Configures the MongoDB client, including custom converters for OffsetDateTime.

5.1.7 MongoDB Integration

MongoDB is used to store alarms and acknowledged alarms. The application connects to MongoDB using Spring Data MongoDB, with custom configurations provided in the MongoConfig class.

5.2 Service Quality Management Service

The Service Quality Management project provides a robust and scalable system for managing Service Level Objectives (SLO) and Service Level Specifications (SLS). The Service Quality Management Service handles high volumes of data, processes service levels, and stores them in MongoDB. It exposes RESTful endpoints for managing SLOs and SLSs.

5.2.1 Architecture

The architecture of the Service Quality Management Service is designed for scalability and maintainability. It includes:

- **Spring Boot Application:** Core logic for service level management.
- **MongoDB:** Database for storing SLOs and SLSs.
- **Docker:** Containerization for consistent deployment.
- **Kubernetes:** Orchestration for deployment, scaling, and management.

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Figure 3. QoS Architecture

5.2.2 API Models

The API models define the structure of the data used in the Service Quality Management Service. Key models include:

- **ServiceLevelObjective:** Represents a service level objective with details such as conformance targets, thresholds, and periods.
- **ServiceLevelSpecification:** Represents a service level specification with related objectives and valid periods.
- **ServiceLevelObjectiveCreate:** DTO for creating SLOs.
- **ServiceLevelObjectiveUpdate:** DTO for updating SLOs.
- **ServiceLevelSpecificationCreate:** DTO for creating SLSSs.
- **ServiceLevelSpecificationUpdate:** DTO for updating SLSSs.

5.2.3 Repositories

Repositories provide CRUD operations for MongoDB collections:

- **ServiceLevelObjectiveRepository:** Manages ServiceLevelObjective entities.
- **ServiceLevelSpecificationRepository:** Manages ServiceLevelSpecification entities.

5.2.4 Services

Services contain the business logic and interact with repositories:

- **Create Service Level Objective (SLO):** Creates a new SLO.

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- **Get All Service Level Objectives:** Retrieves all SLOs.
- **Get Service Level Objective By ID:** Retrieves a specific SLO by its ID.
- **Update Service Level Objective:** Updates an existing SLO.
- **Delete Service Level Objective:** Deletes an SLO.
- **Create Service Level Specification (SLS):** Creates a new SLS.
- **Get All Service Level Specifications:** Retrieves all SLSs.
- **Get Service Level Specification By ID:** Retrieves a specific SLS by its ID.
- **Update Service Level Specification:** Updates an existing SLS.
- **Delete Service Level Specification:** Deletes an SLS.

Method	Endpoint	Description
POST	/slos	Creates a new Service Level Objective based on the provided parameters.
GET	/slos	Retrieves all Service Level Objectives from the database.
GET	/slos/{id}	Retrieves a specific Service Level Objective by its ID.
PUT	/slos/{id}	Updates an existing Service Level Objective based on the provided parameters.
DELETE	/slos/{id}	Deletes a Service Level Objective by its ID.
POST	/slss	Creates a new Service Level Specification based on the provided parameters.
GET	/slss	Retrieves all Service Level Specifications from the database.
GET	/slss/{id}	Retrieves a specific Service Level Specification by its ID.
PUT	/slss/{id}	Updates an existing Service Level Specification based on the provided parameters.
DELETE	/slss/{id}	Deletes a Service Level Specification by its ID.

Table 3. QoS services

5.2.5 Utilities

Utilities provide helper methods and configurations:

- **ServiceLevelObjectiveMongoAdapter:** Converts between API models and MongoDB models for SLOs.

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- **ServiceLevelSpecificationMongoAdapter**: Converts between API models and MongoDB models for SLSSs.
- **ErrorResponseUtil**: Creates error responses for exceptions.
- **MongoConfig**: Configures MongoDB connection and custom converters.
- **OffsetDateTimeCodec**: Custom codec for OffsetDateTime.

5.2.6 Configuration

- **MongoConfig**: Configures the MongoDB client, including custom converters for OffsetDateTime.

5.2.7 MongoDB Integration

MongoDB is used to store SLOs and SLSSs. The application connects to MongoDB using Spring Data MongoDB, with custom configurations provided in the MongoConfig class.

6. Holoportation Metrics

Holoportation metrics are critical for ensuring the quality of experience in 6G networks. These metrics include Frame Per Second (FPS), Throughput, and Latency.

As specified by I2CAT for holoportation, the focus is on three primary KPIs critical to the user experience:

- **Frame Per Second (FPS):** Essential for smooth visual motion, targeting more than 30 FPS for minimal quality and striving for 60 FPS for optimal experiences.
- **Server-side Perceived Throughput:** Measures the data transmission capacity, crucial for maintaining high-resolution image quality. The expected range is 30 to 50 Mbps (compressed) for standard operations, expanding up to 100 Gbps to 1 Tbps (raw) for delivering ultra-high-definition images.
- **Frame Delay:** Incorporates both end-to-end latency (< 50–100 ms) and motion-to-photon latency (< 15 ms), critical for real-time interaction synchronization in holoportation, enhancing immersion and reducing user disorientation.

The specific ranges for these KPIs are summarized in the following table:

KPI	Range
Frame per Second (FPS)	> 30 FPS
Server-side perceived throughput per second	30 to 50 Mbps (compressed) ⁶ , 100 Gbps to 1 Tbps (raw) ⁷
Frame delay	< 50–100 ms end-to-end latency and <15 ms motion-to-photon latency ^{8,9}

Table 4. KPIs for Holoportation

⁶ "Microsoft holoportation. <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/research/project/holoportation-3/>," Accessed: 5 Feb. 2023.

⁷ X. Xu, Y. Pan, P. P. M. Y. Lwin, and X. Liang, "3d holographic display and its data transmission requirement," in International Conference on Information Photonics and Optical Communications, Oct 2011, pp. 1–4

⁸T. Rhee, et al., "Augmented virtual teleportation for high-fidelity telecollaboration," IEEE Trans. Vis. Comput. Graph. 2020, 26, 1923–1933

⁹ Hatim Chergui, Adriana Fernandez, "6GENABLERS-E2.1 Use Case Definition Report", 2023.

7. Workflow and Integration

7.1 Telemetry Data Collection

1. **Data Collection:** OpenTelemetry Collectors gather raw telemetry data (FPS, Throughput, Latency) from the holoportation services.
2. **Data Enrichment:** The collected data is enriched with metadata for better analysis and correlation.

7.2 ETL Process

1. **Extract:** Data is extracted from the observability backend (Prometheus, InfluxDB).
2. **Transform:** Data is transformed to the required format for analysis.
3. **Load:** Transformed data is loaded into the analytics services for processing.

7.3 Analytics Service Integration

1. **Thresholds and SLOs:** The Service Quality Management Service defines thresholds and SLOs for each metric.
2. **Monitoring and Alarming:** The Alarm Service monitors the metrics against the defined SLOs. If an SLO is violated, an alarm is raised by ETL.

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7.4 MongoDB Integration

MongoDB is used to store telemetry data and configuration details. The application connects to MongoDB using Spring Data MongoDB, with custom configurations provided in the MongoConfig class.

7.5 Docker Configuration

The application is containerized using Docker. The Dockerfile for both services is:

```
# Use the official Maven image to create a build artifact
FROM maven:3.8.5-openjdk-17 AS build
WORKDIR /app
COPY pom.xml .
COPY src ./src
RUN mvn clean package -DskipTests
# Use the official OpenJDK image to run the application
FROM openjdk:17-jdk-slim
VOLUME /tmp
COPY --from=build /app/target/*.jar app.jar
COPY src/main/resources/application.properties /app/application.properties
RUN apt-get update && apt-get install -y curl
ENTRYPOINT ["java", "-jar", "/app.jar"]
```

8. Kubernetes Deployment

8.1 Preparing the Environment

1. **Install Docker:** Ensure Docker is installed on your machine.
2. **Install Kubernetes:** Set up a Kubernetes cluster (e.g., using Minikube or a managed service like GKE).
3. **Install kubectl:** Command-line tool for interacting with Kubernetes.

8.2 Building and Pushing Docker Images

1. **Build the Docker Image:**

```
docker build -t your-repo/<service-name>:latest .
```

2. **Push the Docker Image to a Registry:**

```
docker push your-repo/<service-name>:latest
```

8.3 Deploying MongoDB

Create a Kubernetes deployment for MongoDB:

```
apiVersion: apps/v1
kind: Deployment
metadata:
  name: mongodb
spec:
  replicas: 1
  selector:
    matchLabels:
      app: mongodb
  template:
    metadata:
      labels:
        app: mongodb
    spec:
      containers:
        - name: mongodb
          image: mongo:latest
          ports:
            - containerPort: 27017
          volumeMounts:
            - name: mongo-storage
              mountPath: /data/db
      volumes:
        - name: mongo-storage
```

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```
    persistentVolumeClaim:
      claimName: mongo-pvc
---
apiVersion: v1
kind: Service
metadata:
  name: mongodb-service
spec:
  selector:
    app: mongoddb
  ports:
  - port: 27017
    targetPort: 27017
---
apiVersion: v1
kind: PersistentVolumeClaim
metadata:
  name: mongo-pvc
spec:
  accessModes:
  - ReadWriteOnce
  resources:
    requests:
      storage: 1Gi
```

Apply the configuration:

```
kubectl apply -f mongodb-deployment.yaml
kubectl apply -f mongo-pvc.yaml
```

8.4 Deploying the Alarm Service

```
apiVersion: apps/v1
kind: Deployment
metadata:
  name: alarmservices
  namespace: analytics-service
spec:
  replicas: 1
  selector:
    matchLabels:
      app: alarmservices
  template:
    metadata:
      labels:
        app: alarmservices
    spec:
```

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```
containers:
  - name: alarmservices
    image: localhost:32000/alarmservices:latest
    ports:
      - containerPort: 8080
    imagePullPolicy: Always
    env:
      - name: SPRING_DATA_MONGODB_URI
        value: "mongodb://mongo.analytics-
service.svc.cluster.local:27017/alarmservices?connectTimeoutMS=30000&socketTimeout
MS=30000"
---
apiVersion: v1
kind: Service
metadata:
  name: alarmservices
  namespace: analytics-service
spec:
  type: NodePort
  selector:
    app: alarmservices
  ports:
    - protocol: TCP
      port: 8080
      targetPort: 8080
      nodePort: 30109
---
apiVersion: v1
kind: Service
metadata:
  name: alarmservices-internal
  namespace: analytics-service
spec:
  selector:
    app: alarmservices
  ports:
    - name: alarmservices-internal
      port: 8080
```

Apply the configuration:

```
kubectl apply -f alarm-service-deployment.yaml
```

8.5 Deploying the Service Quality Management Service

```
apiVersion: apps/v1
kind: Deployment
```

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```
metadata:
  name: qos
  namespace: analytics-service
spec:
  replicas: 1
  selector:
    matchLabels:
      app: qos
  template:
    metadata:
      labels:
        app: qos
    spec:
      containers:
        - name: qos
          image: localhost:32000/qos:latest
          ports:
            - containerPort: 8080
          imagePullPolicy: Always
          env:
            - name: SPRING_DATA_MONGODB_URI
              value: "mongodb://mongo.analytics-
service.svc.cluster.local:27017/qos?connectTimeoutMS=30000&socketTimeoutMS=30000
"
---
apiVersion: v1
kind: Service
metadata:
  name: qos
  namespace: analytics-service
spec:
  type: NodePort
  selector:
    app: qos
  ports:
    - protocol: TCP
      port: 8080
      targetPort: 8080
      nodePort: 30110
---
apiVersion: v1
kind: Service
metadata:
  name: qos-internal
  namespace: analytics-service
spec:
  selector:
```

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```
app: qos
ports:
- name: qos-internal
  port: 8080
```

Apply the configuration:

```
kubectl apply -f service-quality-management-service-deployment.yaml
```

8.6 Configuring and Accessing the Services

1. Verify the Deployments:

```
kubectl get deployments
kubectl get pods
kubectl get services
```

2. **Access the Service:**

- **Quality Management Service:** The service can be accessed via the NodePort assigned for external access and ClusterIP for internal access. For example, if the NodePort is 30109, you can access the service at **<http://<node-ip>:30109>**.
- **Alarm Service:** The service can be accessed via the NodePort assigned for external access and ClusterIP for internal access. For example, if the NodePort is `30110`, you can access the service at <http://<node-ip>:30110>.

9.JSON API Definitions and Explanations

9.1 Service Level Specification (SLS) Example

Parameter	Description	Source	Type
id	Unique identifier for the SLS	Generated by the system	String
href	URI reference for the SLS	Generated by the system	String
description	Description of the SLS	User-provided	String
name	Name of the SLS	User-provided	String
relatedServiceLevelObjective	List of related SLOs	Defined by user and linked to existing SLOs	List<RelatedSLO>
validFor	Time period for which the SLS is valid	User-provided	TimePeriod
@baseType	Base type of the entity	Default value	String
@schemaLocation	URI for the schema location	Default value	String
@type	Type of the entity	Default value	String

Table 5. Service Level Specification (SLS) Parameters

9.2 Service Level Objective (SLO) Example

Parameter	Description	Source	Type
id	Unique identifier for the SLO	Generated by the system	String
href	URI reference for the SLO	Generated by the system	String
conformanceComparator	Comparator used for conformance check	User-provided	String

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conformanceTarget	Target value for conformance	User-provided	String
graceTimes	Number of grace times allowed	User-provided	Integer
name	Name of the SLO	User-provided	String
thresholdTarget	Threshold value for the SLO	User-provided	String
toleranceTarget	Tolerance value for the SLO	User-provided	String
conformancePeriod	Time period for conformance	User-provided	TimePeriod
serviceLevelObjectiveConsequence	List of consequences for SLO violations	User-provided	List<Consequence>
serviceLevelObjectiveParameter	Parameters defining the SLO	User-provided	Parameter
tolerancePeriod	Time period for tolerance	User-provided	TimePeriod
validFor	Time period for which the SLO is valid	User-provided	TimePeriod
@baseType	Base type of the entity	Default value	String
@schemaLocation	URI for the schema location	Default value	String
@type	Type of the entity	Default value	String

Table 6. Service Level Objective (SLO) Parameters

9.3 Alarm Example

Parameter	Description	Source	Type
state	State of the alarm	Generated by the system based on SLO violation	String
alarmType	Type of the alarm	Defined by the system	String

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perceivedSeverity	Perceived severity of the alarm	Derived from SLO severity	String
probableCause	Probable cause of the alarm	Based on SLO violation details	String
specificProblem	Specific problem description	Based on SLO details	String
sourceSystemId	Source system identifier	Based on related entity in SLO	String
alarmDetails	Detailed description of the alarm	Generated based on metric comparisons	String
alarmRaisedTime	Time when the alarm was raised	Generated by the system	DateTime
alarmChangedTime	Last time the alarm state changed	Generated by the system	DateTime
alarmClearedTime	Time when the alarm was cleared	Generated by the system	DateTime
alarmReportingTime	Time when the alarm was reported	Generated by the system	DateTime
ackState	Acknowledgment state of the alarm	Default value	String
ackSystemId	System that acknowledged the alarm	Default value	String
affectedService	List of affected services	Based on related entity in SLO	List<ServiceRef>
alarmEscalation	Indicates if the alarm has been escalated	Default value	Boolean
crossedThresholdInformation	Information about crossed thresholds	Generated by the system based on SLO violation	List<ThresholdInfo>
isRootCause	Indicates if this alarm is the root cause	Default value	Boolean
plannedOutageIndicator	Indicates planned outage status	Default value	String

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proposedRepairedActions	Proposed actions to repair the issue	Generated based on affected metrics	String
serviceAffecting	Indicates if the issue is affecting the service	Default value	Boolean

Table 7. Alarm Parameters

10. Conclusion

This document provides a comprehensive overview of the E5.4 High Precision Smart Telemetry project, including the architecture, deployment, and integration details for the Alarm Service and Service Quality Management Service. It also explains how the system integrates with the E3.6.1 Final design for data management and adaptive learning in 6G. By following this guide, you should be able to understand and deploy the components successfully, ensuring high precision and reliable telemetry and service level management.